

MORPHOMETRIC PARAMETERS OF THE KIDNEYS OF RATS DURING CORRECTION OF POLAR EXPOSURE TO ALCOHOL IN THE AGE ASPECT

Khamroev I.S.
Teshaev Sh.Zh.

Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan
Bukhara State Medical Institute
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10147425>

Relevance: An estimated 2.3 billion people currently drink alcohol. In three WHO regions – the Americas, European and Western Pacific – more than half the population consumes alcohol. Europe has the highest per capita alcohol consumption in the world, despite a decline of more than 10% since 2010. Harmful use of alcohol is responsible for more than 200 diseases and injuries. Globally, 3 million people die each year as a result of the harmful use of alcohol, accounting for 5.3% of all deaths. Overall, alcohol consumption accounts for 5.1% of the global burden of disease and injury, as estimated by disability-adjusted life years (DALYs). In addition to its health consequences, harmful alcohol use causes significant social and economic harm to individuals and society as a whole. Alcohol use causes death and disability relatively early in life. Among people aged 20 to 39 years, approximately 13.5% of all deaths are related to alcohol use.

Purpose of the study: study of the morphometric parameters of the kidneys of white laboratory rats during correction of the polar effects of alcohol in the age aspect.

Materials and research methods: We selected 128 mature outbred white rats of both sexes, whose age ranged from 3 to 12 months, weighing 200 g, raised under standard vivarium conditions for experimental scientific research. Laboratory animals were kept in the vivarium of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. The rats were kept in special rooms (room temperature 20-24°C, humidity 60%, illumination 12 hours) in accordance with the requirements for experimental animals.

Conclusion: the highest rate of increase in the thickness of the renal capsule in the lower pole of the kidneys is noticeable at 3 months of age (27.9%) in the upper pole (22.2%) and the smallest in the hilum of the kidneys (18.8%). The greatest thickness of the cortical layer can be seen in the lower pole of the kidneys (15.8%). A subtle increase is observed at the hilum of the kidneys. In the renal medulla, the highest growth rate was observed in the upper (15.8%) 12-

month age, and in the lower pole (21.2%) and at the renal hilum (12.9%) at 6-month age.

List of used literature:

1. Abdurakhmanova D.B. et al. Features of microcirculation of the fibrous capsule of the kidney during oral exposure to sodium nitrite //Volgograd Medical Scientific Journal. – 2020. – No. 1. – pp. 36-40.
2. Antonova V. M. et al. Morphofunctional state of the kidneys at the stage of structural disorders of light desynchronosis in an experiment // Modern problems of science and education. – 2017. – No. 1. P.62
3. Babanin A.A., Ulanov V.S. On the morphology of changes in the testicles of experimental animals during chronic alcohol poisoning // Crimean Journal of Experimental and Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – T. 10. – No. 4. – pp. 5-9.
4. Kursov S.V. Acute alcohol poisoning. Emergency Medicine 2012. - No. 7-8 – pp. 46-47.
5. Moiseev V.S. Alcohol disease. Damage to internal organs // GEOTAR-Media. - Moscow. - 2014. – P. 480.
6. Okulova I.I. et al. The influence of alcohol on the body // International student scientific bulletin. – 2017. – No. 5. P. 8
7. Osminkin V.A. Some histological criteria for kidney and liver damage in death from acute ethyl alcohol poisoning // Forensic medical examination. – 2015. – T. 58. – No. 1. – pp. 18-21.
8. Pavlova T.V. et al. Pathomorphological mechanisms of kidney participation in the multimorbid continuum of a person during surgical trauma // Fundamental Research. – 2012. – No. 8-1. – pp. 131-134.

